

Study of Physical Properties, Chemicals and Sensory with Various Gum Additional Variation in Beetroot (*Beta vulgaris* L.) with Addition of Cinnamon Extract (*Cinnamomum* *burmannii*)

*¹Safira, ²Kawiji, ³Siswanti

^{*1}Departement of Culinary Art, Polytechnic Nest

^{2,3}Departement of Food Science and Technology, Sebelas Maret University

Corresponding Email : Safira@politekniknest.ac.id

Abstract:

This study aims to determine the effect of gum arab concentration and the addition of cinnamon extract to the sensory, physical and chemical properties contained in the beetroot jam (*Beta vulgaris* L.). This study used Completely Randomized Design (RAL) with 3 treatments based on different concentrations of gum arab. The treatment is: F1 (0.5% gum arab), F2 (1% gum arab), F3 (1.5% gum arab). This research uses 6 analyzes consisting of total dissolved solids, antioxidant activity, water content, water activity, viscosity and sensory test. Statistical analysis of data with ANOVA at $\alpha = 5\%$. The results of analysis showed that the use of gum arab can reduce the amount of water activity contained in the beetroot jam, so the shelf life of the beetroot jam can last longer. In addition, the use of gum arabic in moisture content did not give significant effect to the beetroot jam obtained, while the viscosity, the total amount of dissolved solids, the antioxidant activity had a significant effect with the addition of gum arab concentration. The optimal use of gum arab was obtained at 1.5% gum arab concentration from multiple comparison test. The use of gum arab concentration of 1.5% is the maximum concentration of the use of gum arabic concentration to beet tuber jam. The use of concentration of 1.5% gum arab is very influential on the five parameters used are aroma, taste, texture, color and overalls.

Keywords: *Beetroot Jam, Cinnamon Extract, Gum Arab*

JGHTT (Journal of Global Hospitality and Tourism Technology)

Vol 1 Issue 1 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12590364](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12590364)

Received: 25/05/24 Revised: 25/05/24 Accepted: 26/05/24 Online: 29/06/24

© 2024 The Authors. Published by Politeknik Nest. This is an open-access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

The beet plant (*Beta vulgaris* L.) is a plant with roots, similar to red tubers. The shape tends to be round and resembles a red (purple) sweet potato. Beets are rich in carbohydrates with low calorie content, a specific color fiber, namely deep purplish red. The purplish red color of beets is caused by a combination of the purple pigment betacyanin and the yellow pigment betaxanthin. From 100 grams of beetroot, the nutritional content is obtained, namely protein, fat, calcium, phosphorus, iron, vitamin A, vitamin B, vitamin C, water and the largest content is starch of 35.81% and fiber of 2.14% from 100 grams of weight of ingredients. (Annisa, 2011). The starch contained in beets greatly influences the gelatinization process when making dough for products such as jam, ice cream, sweets and fruit leather.

Beets are an annual plant in the form of grass, beet stems are very short, almost invisible. The taproot grows into a tuber. The leaves grow collected at the neck of the taproot (base of the tuber) and are reddish in color. There are 2 varieties of beets (*Beta vulgaris* L. var. *rubra* L.) whose tubers are dark red. Meanwhile, white beets or cut beets (*Beta vulgaris* L. var. *varicla* L.) have whitish red tubers. In Indonesia, these two types of beets cannot flower and produce seeds, so the seeds are still imported from abroad. Beetroots are round or resemble a top. However, there are also those that are oval in shape. The tip of the beet tuber has roots. The flowers are arranged in a series of flowers with many long stems (racemes). This plant has difficulty flowering in Indonesia. Beets are popular because they taste delicious, slightly sweet and soft (Asian Journal, 2019). The use of beet tubers is currently very limited because people are not very familiar with beet tubers, apart from that, beet tubers also have a rather annoying flavor, namely an unpleasant taste that cannot be lost during processing. Existing applications of beets in the food industry include beet plant extract as a purplish-red natural dye. Apart from that, processing beetroot can extend the shelf life of the beetroot itself because basically tubers, vegetables and tubers are easily damaged. This is because tubers, vegetables and tubers are still carrying out post-harvest metabolic activities which, if not processed immediately, will cause damage.

am is a type of processed food that comes from crushed fruit juice or fruit, added sugar and cooked until thickened.

Jam is not consumed directly, but is used as a complementary ingredient in white bread or as a filler in sweet bread, pineapple cakes or as a sweetener in drinks such as yogurt or ice cream (Lies, 2021). Jam is a processed product from pureed fruit or vegetables with a mixture of sucrose sugar and stabilizers which is cooked to obtain a food product with a smooth texture. The texture of jam products is greatly influenced by the following factors: sugar content, type and amount of stabilizer and the heating method applied.

In general, making your own jam according to (Fadhiel and Fahrizal, 2024) begins by selecting ripe fruit, sorting it to select fresh and undamaged fruit, then peeling it and washing it using clean water and draining it until dry. Then, for the blanching treatment, blanching is carried out for 10 minutes at a temperature of 82-1000C by steaming the fruit at a temperature of 1000C. After that, the blanched fruit is crushed with a blender for 3 minutes until it forms puree. Preheat for 5-10 minutes, then add sugar and stabilizer according to the treatment (add stabilizer 0%, 0.5%, 1% and 1.5%). And then heat it over medium heat until the jam is cooked. To assess whether the jam is cooked, use the spoon test, namely by inserting a spoon into the cooking jam. Next, lift the spoon and if the jam between the spoons doesn't flow down, it means the jam is cooked. The best texture of jam is obtained if the soluble solids content is at least 65% (BSN, 1995). According to Buckle et al (1987), the special structure of fruit jam products is due to the formation of a pectin-sugar-acid gel complex. The mechanism of gel formation from pectin-sugar-acid water is that in one fruit substrate the acid, pectin, is a negatively charged colloid. The sugar added in this process will affect the existing pectin-water balance, also eliminating the stability of the pectin. The pectin will clump and form fine fibers, this structure is able to hold liquid. Pectin levels in large quantities can determine the level of continuity and density of the fibers formed. Good quality jam is characterized by brilliant color, even distribution of fruit, soft texture, natural fruit taste, does not experience syneresis and crystallization during storage (Cross, 2019).

Sugar in making frozen food products can be used as a sweetener and can improve body and texture. Sugar can help prevent large ice crystals from forming during freezing. Increasing sugar levels will result in body viscosity and strength. Apart from that, the main function of sugar as a sweetener plays an important role because it can increase the acceptability of a food, namely by masking unpleasant flavors. The sweet taste of sucrose is pure because there is no after taste. In ice cream products, apart from increasing product acceptance through a sweet effect, sugar also functions to improve the shape and texture of the product and has an effect on the freezing point. The high sugar content, presence of acid and pectin from beet tubers can be used as processed jam products. Because this is a requirement for gel formation for making jam. This is in accordance with Desrosier's (1988) statement, namely that jam can be formed if the appropriate levels of pectin, sugar and acid in the water are reached. Making jam from beetroot can be used as a functional food, which provides health benefits and as a form of diversification from beetroot so that it can increase its added value. However, the taste and smell of beetroot is not liked by consumers. Therefore, beet tubers should be combined to reduce the unpleasant aroma and taste. To reduce the unpleasant aroma and taste, in research on making beetroot jam, cinnamon was added. Cinnamon oil is mostly used

in the flavor industry, including as a spice in meat and ready-to-eat foods, sauces, cola-like drinks, confectionery, tobacco flavor and in pharmaceutical and dental preparations (Guenther, 1990). Senayake and Johnson (1978) reported that the main contents of stem bark oil and root bark oil of *C. zeylanicum* were cinnamaldehyde (75%) and camphor (56%). *C. zeylanicum* bark oil has a pleasant spicy aroma and tastes sharp and sweet. Mallavarapu et al. (1995) have identified 53 compounds that make up *C. zeylanicum* leaf oil with the main content being eugenol (81–84.5%). *C. zeylanicum* leaf oil tastes warm, spicy and smells fragrant and very sharp. So, cinnamon is added to beetroot jam to improve the poor taste of beetroot jam and also to get a product that has better functional value. Spices contain active components which are believed to have quite high amounts of antioxidant activity. Cinnamon is a plant that has been used for a long time as a cooking spice and traditional herbal medicine. *Cinnamomum burmannii* is a type of cinnamon originating from Indonesia. Cinnamon bark, leaves and oil are processed and used as food and drink flavorings, and are widely used in the cosmetics sector. Apart from that, cinnamon is also beneficial for health, including having the effect of protecting the stomach (Walangitan et al, 2023).

One of the important components in making jam is a stabilizer. Stabilizers are used to prevent the formation of coarse crystals, form a soft texture, produce a uniform product and provide better resistance to damage and make it easier to handle (Bahramparvar and Tehrani, 2021). According to Buckle (2020), the stabilizers usually used in jam are gelatin, CMC, carrageenan and gum. Gum arabic is composed of proteins that are covalently bound to macromolecular components (Glicksman, 2020). Proteins have amino groups and hydroxyl groups which are hydrophilic, these groups can form hydrogen bonds with one or more water molecules, so they are able to absorb water and hold it in a molecular structure and form a thick colloid with a gel structure (Winarno, 2019). The addition of gum arabic to beetroot jam with the addition of gum arabic and cinnamon extract can increase the total solids in beetroot jam. The increase in total solids in the product means that the water content in the jam decreases.

The addition of citric acid also plays a role in reducing the water content of beetroot jam because citric acid is. However, the use of citric acid in beetroot jam had no effect because the amount of citric acid used was the same for all treatments adding gum arabic. Apart from adding citric acid, the long heating process also reduces the water content. Gum arabic is widely used as a stabilizer for foods such as ice cream and jam because of its ability to absorb water. During the formation of the gelatin in the jam, the dough expands so that it contains many lumps which tend to gather to form larger lumps and give a rough texture. The addition of gum arabic aims to prevent the formation of larger gel lumps by binding a certain amount of water. Using gum arabic will also give the jam a better texture (Nugraha, 2023).

Jam products are richer in natural fiber and vitamins. This opens up opportunities for jam products as functional foods that are healthy and affordable as well as tasting delicious, and most importantly can be accepted by the wider community and have higher economic value (Ahza et al, 2005). In general, making fruit jam requires the main raw material, namely beet seeds, and supporting raw materials such as sugar, stabilizer, citric acid and water.

Research Method

Tool

The tools used are divided into two types, namely tools used for making jam, including a juicer (Kitchen Set Juicer), steaming pan, spoon, glass, basin, knife, thermometer (Pyrex), and tools used for analysis, among others. measuring cup, set of water content method tools with distillation (sterling-bidwell), analytical balance (AND-GF300), electric stove, Kjeldahl flask, filter paper, volume pipette, propipet, beaker, stirrer, Erlenmeyer, water bath, extraction tool soxhlet, litmus paper, spatula, test tube, vortex, volumetric flask, funnel, UV- VIS spectrophotometer, Refractometer, AW meter, Tray Viscometer, plate and form.

Material

The ingredients used in making jam are beetroot (*Beta Vulgaris L.*), sugar, gum Arabic, citric acid, water, cinnamon (*Cinnamomum burmannii*) as well as other analytical ingredients: xylene, distilled water, concentrated HCl solution, bromophenol blue indicator, sodium acetate, DPPH(1,1- diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl)

The stages of this research can be seen in Figure 1 below :

Figure 1 The stages of research

Result and Discussion

The initial stage of research carried out was making cinnamon extract. The cinnamon used is dry cinnamon sticks. First the cinnamon was washed, then weighed 5 g. After that, add 100 ml of water to the pan and boil until it boils. The boiled cinnamon extract is then filtered and 50 ml is taken. Making beetroot jam begins with sorting to obtain tubers that are in good condition and intact. Peel the skin of the red beetroot which is in good condition and intact, wash it and steam it for 30 minutes and mash it with a blender with the addition of 200 ml of water until you get beetroot pulp. The beet root pulp obtained was added with 40 g of sugar. The addition of sugar is based on the tuber puree used in making beetroot jam. After that the resulting mixture was then cooked in the first stage for 3 minutes and the second cooking for 30 minutes with gum arabic as much as (0.5%, 1% and 1.5%), 1% citric acid, and 50 ml of cinnamon extract after it is stirred until homogeneous. The homogeneous mixture is then removed and cooled to room temperature before being packaged then physical analysis was carried out including water content using thermovolumetric method (AOAC, 1997), total dissolved solids using a refractometer (Apriyantoro, 1989) while antioxidant activity using a spectrophotometer with DPPH reagent (Lai et al. in Supriyono (2018), activity water using aw meter (Apriyantono, 1989), while viscosity using a viscometer (Apriyantono, 1989) and organoleptic testing with Multiple Comparison Test Next, the sensory, physical and chemical analysis data obtained were collected and processed and analyzed statistically using the one way ANOVA method. The chemical test taken was based on the 2 best results, namely beetroot jam with the addition of 0.5 and 1% gum arabic, seen from the liking test. Chemical testing aims to determine changes in product quality from beetroot jam with the addition of cinnamon extract and gum arabic. The chemical analyzes analyzed include; water content, total dissolved solids, water activity, viscosity, and antioxidant activity. The samples used were the two best samples most liked by the panelists according to SPSS with Duncan, namely with the addition of cinnamon extract and gum arabic.

If it shows significant results, it is continued with a real difference test using the Multiple Comparison Test at a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. which can be seen in the table below :

Table 1. Chemical Characteristics of Beetroot Jam with Variations in Adding Gum Arabic to Beetroot Jam (*Beta Vulgaris L.*) with the Addition of Cinnamon Extract (*Cinnamomum burmanii*)

Characteristic	Unit	Addition of Gum Arabic	
		F1	F2
Water Activities	-	0,89 ± 0,19	0,90 ± 0,01
Antioxydant Activity	%	48,29± 0,79	48,86 ± 0,37
Water Content	%	44,95± 1,30	44,85 ± 1,53

It can be seen in Table 1 that the experimental value 1 is 0.89 ± 0.19 . Meanwhile, in beetroot jam with the addition of gum arabic there is no decrease in aw because gum arabic is less able to bind water at a concentration of less than 1% so that the free water contained does not become smaller and as a result the Aw value does not decrease. At concentrations of 0.5 and 1%, there is a decrease in water content, but because the water binding ability of gum arabic is low, the free water contained in beetroot jam does not become smaller so it does not cause a decrease in the Aw value. The water activity of materials is closely related to water content, which can generally describe the growth of bacteria, fungi and other microbes. In general, the higher the water activity, the more bacteria will grow, while fungi, on the other hand, do not like water activity that is too high. This research is in accordance with research by Legowo and Nurmanto (2024) which states that the higher the water content, the higher the aw value. The results of

the water content in the research were not in accordance with the standards of the National Standardization Agency for tuber jam, namely with a maximum of 35% in the SNI for Tuber Jam, while the results from research on formula 1 with F1 in the attachment showed a water content of 44.95% and research on formula 2 with F2 is 44.85%. Beetroot jam uses beetroot with a high water content, apart from that it uses cinnamon extract which also contains water, so the water content in beetroot jam is high. Gum arabic added to beetroot jam does not have much effect on lowering the water content. Matter This is because the added gum has a low water binding ability compared to other stabilizers. The lower the water content value, the better, because microbes will grow quickly if a product has a high water content value. Meanwhile, the results of the free radical capture analysis for beetroot jam can be seen in Table 1, namely 48.29% when using 0.5% gum arabic and when using 1% gum arabic, the results were 48.86%. This indicates the high amount of antioxidants in beetroot jam because cinnamon extract also contains phenols which are a source of natural antioxidants. Apart from that, there is also a high antioxidant content in beetroot in the form of betanin which is a pigment in beetroot, namely two groups of betaxanthin and bet alain which are makes a high contribution to antioxidants in beets, especially red beets. Red beets have antioxidant levels of around 1.98 mmol/100 grams (Nemzer et al., 2021). Further research was carried out on testing the chemical properties of beetroot jam. The results of this research can be seen in table 2 below

Table 2. Chemical Characteristics of Beetroot Jam with Variations in Adding Gum Arabic to Beetroot Jam (*Beta Vulgaris L.*) with the Addition of Cinnamon Extract (*Cinnamomum burmanii*)

Characteristic	Unit	Addition of Gum Arabic	
		F1	F2
Total Dissolved Solids	Brix	64,3 ^o ±1,29	64,5 ^o ± 2,1
Viscosity	cP	7919,3±133,40	9694,45±102,36

The soluble solids analysis of beetroot jam can be seen in Table 2. Namely, 0.5% gum arabic yield was obtained at 64.3% and 1% arabic gum yield was 64.5%, this is almost close to the total soluble solids determined by SNI, namely a minimum of 65%. This is because gum has less than optimal water absorbing properties compared to other stabilizers. The amount of gum concentration greatly influences the total dissolved solids because the gum will form the texture of the jam thereby increasing the total amount of dissolved solids in the jam.

Furthermore, the results of the viscosity analysis of beetroot jam can be seen in Table 2, namely 96.96 cP with the addition of 1% gum and 79.19 cP with the addition of 0.5% gum. This is in accordance with (Affan, 2008), namely the maximum viscosity of the jam obtained is 90%. The amount of gum arabic added has an effect on the viscosity of beetroot jam. The higher the concentration of gum arabic added, the higher the viscosity obtained, this is in accordance with Gliexman's theory. (1982), namely that stabilizers can increase the viscosity value of jam. According to (Novianti, 2008) the addition of gum arabic will make the jam product more cloudy. These results are not in accordance with the expected results. The expected results with the addition of gum arabic jam will be clearer and brighter so that it can match the jam products on the market. However, based on the sensory tests that have been carried out, according to the panelists, those that are closest to R are samples F1 and F2. This is thought to be because the addition of gum arabic with a higher concentration causes the color of the sample to be browner than R, namely the sample without stabilizer so that the panelists visually prefer F1 and F2 which are closer in color to R. Meanwhile, for the addition of CMC to the previous beetroot jam sample F1 and F2 are closer to R. This is in accordance with Novelina et al. (2010) in Anggraini et al. (2016) if xanthan gum is dissolved in water it will be cream colored, whereas for the CMC stabilizer type, if it is dissolved in water it will become clear so the level of clarity is higher than xanthan gum.

Organoleptic testing is a way of assessing the quality of a product by using the sensitivity of the human senses such as seeing with the eyes, smelling with the nose and tasting with the tongue. The type of organoleptic test carried out in beetroot jam research is a discriminative quality test, namely the difference test. The difference test is a test that is intended to statistically see the differences between samples and a sensitivity test, which measures the ability of panelists to detect a sensory characteristic. The differentiation test used here is the ranking test. The purpose of using the ranking test is to rank coded samples according to their order for a particular sensory trait. This differentiation test with ranking test includes color, aroma, taste, texture and overall. This ranking test quality testing was carried out by 25 untrained panelists. The next research carried out was the Sensory Characteristics of Beetroot Jam with Variations in adding Gum Arabic to Beetroot Jam (*Beta Vulgaris L.*) with the addition of Cinnamon Extract (*Cinnamomum burmanii*) which can be seen in table 3 below:

Table 3. the Sensory Characteristics of Beetroot Jam with Variations in adding Gum Arabic to Beetroot Jam (*Beta Vulgaris L.*) with the addition of Cinnamon Extract (*Cinnamomum burmanii*)

Formulation	Parameter				
	Color	Taste	Arome	Texture	Overall
F1	4,36 ^a	4,60 ^a	5,20 ^a	5,16 ^b	4,00 ^a
F2	4,72 ^a	4,96 ^a	5,08 ^a	3,56 ^a	4,24 ^a
F3	6,08 ^b	5,72 ^a	5,04 ^a	5,80 ^b	6,60 ^b

*Different letter notations in the same column indicate significant differences at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

**1. Strongly Dislike 2. Dislike 3. Normal 4. Like 5. Very Like

***Ranking Test: The largest number indicates the highest level of likeability and is followed by the next smaller number

The results in Table 3 show that from the treatments the concentrations of gum arabic F1, F2, and F3 were not significantly different from R (control). This can be seen from the subset of SPSS processed results in Table 3. This is in accordance with the statement of Piccone et al. (2011) who stated that increasing the amount of hydrocolloids in the food matrix has been shown to increase product thickness which is associated with a reduction in taste perception which can partly be attributed to a decrease in aroma compounds. The results of previous research using CMC also obtained the same results, namely not significantly different from R. In all formulations. According to Ikhwal et al. (2014) the higher the concentration of pectin added, the viscosity increases so that the aroma is retained. Due to the high viscosity, the arome of the jam is retained inside, thus affecting the organoleptic test value of the jam arome.

The aroma of a food determines the deliciousness of the food. Assessing the aroma of food cannot be separated from the function of the sense of smell. According to Winarno (2020), the smell received by the nose and brain is generally a mixture of four main odors, namely fragrant, sour, rancid and burnt. Aroma can also be an indication of product damage, a rancid aroma tends to indicate that the product has been damaged.

Beetroot jam tends to have a distinctive fruity aroma. With the use of cinnamon extract, it is hoped that the aroma of the resulting jam will be stronger, thereby increasing consumers' desire to consume it. Organoleptic testing of aroma parameters was carried out in this research because aroma was carried out in this research because aroma is one of the quality requirements for beetroot jam in accordance with SNI 3746:2008, namely normal aroma. However, by using cinnamon extract in beetroot jam.

Beetroot jam tends to have a distinctive fruity aroma. With the use of cinnamon extract, it is hoped that the aroma of the resulting jam will be stronger, thereby increasing consumers' desire to consume it. Organoleptic testing of aroma parameters was carried out in this research because aroma was carried out in this research because aroma is one of the quality requirements for beetroot jam in accordance with SNI 3746:2008, namely normal aroma. However, by using cinnamon extract in beetroot jam.

The taste results in Table 3 show that from the treatment concentrations of gum arabic F1, F2, and F3 there is no significant difference with R. This can be seen from the subset of processed SPSS results in Table 3. According to (Annisa, 2021) the use of gum arabic is used as a stabilizer in food products so that a good texture is obtained. So it can be concluded that adding gum does not affect the taste of beetroot jam. Previous research with CMC also showed the same results, namely there was no real difference in all formulations with R. Thickening agents have the ability to hold liquid and can improve the texture of jam (Chang et al., 2022). The level of thickening agent in large quantities can determine the level of continuity and density of the fibers formed (Buckle et al., 2021)

From the data in Table 3 it can be concluded that the more gum arabic is used, the greater the level of spreadability of beetroot jam. This is due to the thick liquid that is formed in the gum arabic liquid in beetroot jam which causes the viscosity of beetroot jam to increase (Fadhiel and Fahrizal, 2023) so an appropriate and balanced formulation is needed to obtain the appropriate formulation so that the level of ease of spreading is obtained. expected. Meanwhile, from the results of previous research, the use of CMC in the 3 formulations was not significantly different. It is suspected that the addition of gum arabic at a high concentration caused the jam product to become lumpy. The use of gum arabic is useful for increasing the viscosity of the material and excessive use will cause the material to become rough or lumpy (Imeson, 1992).

From the results of this research on beetroot jam, when compared with other jams, the overall results obtained are almost close to jams sold on the market. This can be seen from the SPSS results of the panelists' acceptance of beetroot jam. In this study, the 2 samples most liked by the panelists, namely samples F1 and F2, were taken from the sensory tests that had been carried out for subsequent chemical and physical analysis. This is because the two samples used have formulations that comply with general jam quality requirements based on sensory tests.

Conclusion

The following conclusions are drawn:

1. The addition of gum arabic affects the physical properties of beetroot jam. The higher the amount of gum arabic used, the lower the water content and the higher the viscosity and total dissolved solids.
2. The addition of gum arabic affects the chemical properties of beetroot jam. The higher the amount of gum arabic used, the higher the water activity and antioxidant activity values.
3. The addition of gum arabic affects the sensory properties of beetroot jam. The higher the amount of gum arabic used affects the sensory properties of beetroot jam
4. The most optimal concentration of the 3 formulations used, namely F1, F2 and F3, is F1.

References

- Affan, Ahmad. 2022. Making Pineapple Jam with the Addition of Siwalan Tubers. *Journal of Food Technology*. Vol.12. Matter. 19–20.
- Anggraini, Ditha Novi., Lilik Eka Radiati and Purwadi. Addition of CMC to Apple Cider Honey Drinks in terms of Taste, Aroma, Color, PH, Viscosity and Turbidity. *Journal of Animal Products Science and Technology*. Vol. 11.No. 1.
- AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemistry). 2020. *Official Methods of Analysis*. 18th edition. Marylan: Association of Official Analytical Chemists inc.
- Apriyantono, A. 1989. *Food Analysis*. Interuniversity Center. Bogor Agricultural Institute. Bogor. Matter. 90
- Astawan, Made. 2018. *Healthy with Fruit*. Jakarta: Dian Rakyat.
- Bahramparvar, Maryam and Mostafa Mazaheri Tehrani. 2021. Application and Function of Stabilizer in Ice Cream. *Food Review International Journal*. Matter. 389–409
- Buckle, K.A. 2022. *Food Science*. Translation: H. Purnomo and Adiono. UI Press. Jakarta. Matter. 220
- Buckle, K.A. and R.A Edward. 2020. *Food Science*. Hari Purnama and Adiono translation. UI Press : Jakarta. Pg 16. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v18i01.375>
- Chang, K. L. B., G. Tsai, J. Lee, and W. Fu. 2019. Heterogenous N-deacetylation of Chitin in Alkaline Solution. *Carb Res*. 303: 327-332.
- Desrosier, N. W., 2018. *Food Preservation Technology*. UI-Press, Jakarta. Pg.4
- Glicksman, M. 2023. *Gum Technology in The Food Industry*. Academic Press. New York. Matter. 45
- Ikhwal, Ahmad P., Zulkifli Lubis, and Sentosa Ginting. Effect of Pectin Concentration and Storage Time on the Quality of Pineapple Jam Sheets. *Journal of Food Engineering*. Vol.2. No. 4.
- Nemzer, Boris., Aneta Sporna Kucab, Zbigniew Pietrzowski, and Stawomir Wybraniec. 2021. Bet alanic and Nutritional Profile of Pigment-Enriched Red Beet Root (*Beta Vulgaris L.*) Dried Extracts. *Journal of Food Chemistry*. Vol. 127. Pg. 42–53.
- Novianti, 2020. Decolorization of Acacia Seyal Gum Arabic. Annual conference of post graduate studies and scientific research hall, Khartoum, Republic of Sudan. Vol. 8. Pg. 17–22.
- Nugraha, Y. P. 2022. The Effect of Cooking Solution Concentration and Its Ratio to Bagasse Weight on the Yield and Physical Properties of Bagasse Pulp (Acetosolv). *Journal of Agricultural Products Technology*. Lampung University. Matter. 58
- Legowo, A. M. and Nurwanto. 2020. *Food Analysis*. Lecture Diktat for the Animal Technology Study Program, Faculty of Animal Husbandry, UNDIP. Semarang.
- Piccone P., S.L. Rastellib, and P. Pittia. 2021. Aroma Release and Sensory Perception of Fruit Candies Model Systems. University of Teramo, Italy. Pg.100.
- Santiago, E.C. dan E.M. Yahlia. 2018. *Identification and quantification of betalains from the fruits of 10 Mexican Prickly Pear Cultivars by High Performance Liquid Chromatography and Electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry*. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Chemistry*. 56(1): 5758-5764

Supriyono, Teguh. 2020. Beta Carotene Content, Total Polyphenols and Free Radical-Eradicating Activity of Mung Bean Milk Kefir (*Vigna radiata*) by the Influence of the Number of Starters (*Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Candida kefir*) and Glucose Concentration. *Journal of Food Technology*. Vol.11. Matter. 95.